

Cool, Long Live

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Abstract

Traditional model suggested that low temperature promote longevity simply by a purely passive thermodynamic, not a genetic, process. However, a recent excellent investigation in Cell journal challenged this hypothesis, indicating that cold temperature actively increased lifespan via a genetic program of TRPA-1-responded, calcium-sensitive signals transferring from PKC-2, SGK-1 to a well-known lifespan regulator of DAF-16. This is very fascinating for lifespan extension, for we may achieve it via a simple cooling measure or taking a tablet if we will have developed a drug against that signaling pathway in the future.

Keywords

Low temperature, lifespan, cation channel, kinase, calcium, TRPA-1, DAF-16, PKC-2, SGK-1

Highlights

1. Genetic control of lifespan extension at low temperature
2. Unexpected function of TRP family channels
3. Unimaginable existence of cold receptors in non-excitable cells
4. Novel modulators of TRPA-1 and PKC-2 in longevity
5. Surprising involvement of calcium signaling pathway in lifespan
6. Presentation of new avenues to investigate lifespan extension

Introduction

Want to live longer, even forever? Two world famous tales exemplified it [1]. Qin Shi Huang, the first ancient Chinese Emperor in the human history almost crazily sought drugs all over the world for living forever. Cleopatra VII, the last pharaoh of ancient Egypt, tried her best to assure perpetual beauty. Despite their power and riches, their dream had not realized. But this dream continues and affects many scientists.

A century ago, a temperature coefficient for the duration of life was first proposed [2,3]. Subsequent experimental evidences in fruit fly [2], fish [4], worm [5] and mouse [6] indicated that lowering temperature prolongs lifespan. These implied a model that lifespan extension observed at low temperature is just the result of a purely passive thermodynamic process. However, two works seemed to argue against that. One is that reducing core body temperature by over-expressing UCP-2 gene in mouse increased lifespan [6], while the other is that AFD neurons sensed high temperature and activated a steroid signaling pathway contributed to anti-aging [7].

Indeed, genetic program is actively involved in lifespan extension at cold temperature, evidenced by

a recent elegant study in *C. elegans*, by Shawn Xu and colleagues, that cold-sensitive TRPA-1 extends lifespan by triggering a cascaded signaling pathway [8]. That makes us closer to our dream of longevity.

Results and Discussions

To uncover the possibility of a genetic program actively promoting longevity at cold temperature, Shawn Xu and colleagues envisioned that there should exist a cold sensor to detect low temperature to "turn on" such a program. They selected TRPA-1, the only known member of transient receptor potential (TRP) superfamily of cation channels in *C. elegans*, as the candidate [9,10]. Knock down/out and over-expression experiments confirmed its role of acting as a cold sensor.

How this turn-on signal is amplified? Transcription factor is such a key candidate. By screening several transcription factors, they verified that DAF-16, a well-known master regulator of lifespan extension [11-13], is involved in low temperature signaling. But as an ion channel, TRPA-1 is unlikely to directly signal to DAF-16. With a smart design, they uncovered that Ca^{2+} is the transmitter of the cold-responded signals. For DAF-16 is best known to be regulated by kinases, they mutated several calcium-sensitive kinases, disclosing the required role of PKC-2 in this signal pathway [14]. However, they failed to detect phosphorylation of DAF-16 by PKC-2 in vitro kinase assays. Further, they assayed several known kinases of DAF-16, and found that SGK-1 can directly phosphorylate DAF-16 [15]. Importantly, human TRPA-1 can functionally substitute that of worm, suggesting a possibly conserved mechanism of TRPA-1 pathway in mammalian.

Till now, the complete signaling pathway of cold sensing is established (Fig.1). That is, low temperatures activate the cold-sensitive channel of TRPA-1, and the ensuing calcium influx via

TRPA-1 then stimulates the calcium-sensitive kinase of PKC-2, which signals via SGK-1 kinase to the transcription factor of DAF-16/FOXO, yielding an extension of lifespan.

Figure 1. Cold temperatures trigger a new signaling pathway to increase lifespan in *C. elegans*. This schematic diagram only shows transcription factor DAF-16/FOXO dependent pathways for life extension. DAF-16/FOXO promotes longevity in response to many inputs. Bright fonts indicate the components of the new reported life-extending pathway by Shawn Xu, while others the previously reported. Cold means low temperature (15-20°C) stress. DR states dietary restriction. Every-other-day feeding and sensory cues exemplify special inputs. TRPA-1, the only known cold-sensitive cation channel in *C. elegans*; Ca²⁺, calcium influx; PKC-2, the sole classical calcium-sensitive PKC (protein kinase C) in *C. elegans*; SGK-1, a DAF-16/ FOXO kinase; DAF-16, a well-known key regulator of lifespan; SIR-2, a sirtuin; HSF-1, a heat-shock transcription factor; LIN-4, a developmental-timing microRNA; AAK-2, a subunit of AMP kinase; JNK-1, Jun kinase 1; TCER-1, a predicted transcription elongation factor; P, phosphorylation. Kinase cascade shows not a protein, but a serial of reaction events associated with many kinases. Black arrow depicts RNA transcribing. Note that some of the proteins listed separately in this figure may act together in the same pathway [8,12].

Among their elegant study, four bright spots for scientific novelty deserve being highlighted, which include a novel function for TRP family channels, and cold receptors surprisingly existed in non-excitable cells exemplified here by intestinal cells, novel modulators of TRPA-1 and PKC-2 in longevity, and unanticipated involvement of calcium signaling pathway in lifespan.

Conclusions and Prospects

Rapid progresses of how reducing food intake, restricting insulin/IGF-1 signaling, slowing mitochondria respiration, and waving off germline function extend lifespan have been made in the past two decades [12,13]. Conversely, very little is known about how temperature reduction promotes longevity. So, a genetic contribution of this TRPA-1 signaling pathway to lifespan extension at low temperatures elegantly detailed by this study is a very big surprise. Not only this surprise, has it also opened up many new avenues, see below:

1. Elucidate the detailed biochemical mechanisms of this model.
2. Identify additional components in the TRPA-1 pathway.
3. Investigate the possible crosstalks of TRPA-1 pathway with well-known dietary restriction, insulin/IGF-1 signaling, mitochondria respiration,

and germline function [12,13]. Among, calcium signals and DAF-16 are two potential convergences.

4. Compare the relative contribution of TRPA-1 and other longevity regulation pathways to lifespan extension [12].
5. Reveal whether the factors regulating calcium signals such as neurotransmitters, neuropeptides, and hormones [16] can modulate lifespan.
6. Uncover otherwise mechanisms underlying lifespan extension at cold temperature, such as other cold-sensitive proteins analogous to TRPA-1.
7. Examine the effects of the intestine as a signaling hub on lifespan modulation [12], such as sensing nutrient components, solution molecules, and physical stimulation.
8. Disclose if a similar phenomenon may occur in other organisms, especially natural mutation of this signaling pathway in long-lived people.
9. Explore whether a simple cooling of the peripheral tissues (e.g. skin and fat [17]) by exposing these animals to cold environments, or decreasing body temperatures by special drugs, affects lifespan.

If all the above mentioned are deciphered fully, our future will possibly give us a surprise of longer lifespan. To that day, Emperor Qin Shi Huang and Queen Cleopatra VII would feel very hurt just because they were born at the wrong time.

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